

On Discontinuity Factor Uncertainties in Triangular Geometries

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ABSTRACT

Recently, Monte Carlo-based reflector discontinuity factors (DCF) were generated in a triangular lattice to verify the values estimated by the PHOENIX5 lattice-physics code for VVER-type reactors. Although good agreement was observed, the generally simpler Monte Carlo approach raised the question of whether MC-based DCFs could eventually replace deterministic lattice-physics-based values.

As a preliminary investigation, this work explored the sensitivity of nodal simulations to DCF uncertainties and examined overall DCF uncertainty by propagating the uncertainty of the underlying tallies. The results indicate that relying on Monte Carlo methods may be feasible within reasonable computing times. However, significant sensitivity was observed for thermal-group corner DCF estimates, particularly with respect to the side segment length.

Keywords: nodal methods, discontinuity factors, monte carlo methods, lattice physics

1. INTRODUCTION

The core simulator POLCA8H developed by Westinghouse Sweden solves the multi-group diffusion equation by dividing each hexagonal assembly into six equilateral triangular nodes, each assigned its own set of nuclear cross sections. The homogeneous solution for each energy group is approximated using eight base functions: two for the axial top and bottom of the node, three for the triangle sides, and three for the triangle corners [1]. Consequently, the simulator requires both side and corner discontinuity factors.

At Westinghouse, POLCA8H is typically supplied with nodal data generated by the lattice-physics code PHOENIX5. Due to its geometric flexibility, PHOENIX5 is also used to implement reflector models for VVER-440 and VVER-1000 reactors. Recently, the CAD2PHX utility tool was developed to facilitate the description and meshing of complex two-dimensional geometries using CAD tools and to automatically generate PHOENIX5 input files [2]. However, these input files remain relatively complex due to the detailed meshing requirements.

Evaluating side and corner discontinuity factors presents a bookkeeping challenge. In addition to tallying nodal cross sections in triangles, heterogeneous fluxes and currents must be evaluated at sides and corners. For the reflector region, discontinuity factors must also be computed using a nodal solver equivalent to POLCA8H.

As part of the verification of PHOENIX5-generated nodal data for the reflector region, Serpent2 [3] was employed to generate reference discontinuity factors. Furthermore, we investigated the feasibility of using Monte Carlo-based discontinuity factors in POLCA8H calculations, which is the subject of this paper.

Using Monte Carlo methods for reflector nodal data generation introduces additional challenges. In particular, the propagation of statistical uncertainties into nodal codes is not widely studied. It is not straightforward to determine the target accuracy for current tallies to ensure nodal results remain

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insensitive to statistical uncertainties. Current work has two objectives: to provide insight into the impact of DCF uncertainties on nodal calculations by using the PHOENIX5/POLCA8H code system and to assess the uncertainty in Monte Carlo-based discontinuity factors by propagating the uncertainties of underlying tallies.

Section 2 introduces the theoretical background and the FULLCORE-440 benchmark, which serves as the test system for this study. Section 3 summarizes the methodology used to evaluate the impact of statistical uncertainties. Section 4 presents preliminary results and discussion.

2. BACKGROUND AND MODELED SYSTEM

2.1. Discontinuity Factors and Corner Currents

In nodal solvers discontinuity factors are used to correct the homogenous nodal solution with the heterogeneous transport solution. Discontinuity factors are defined as:

$$DF_{g,i} = \frac{\phi_{g,i}^{het}}{\phi_{g,i}^{hom}} \quad (1)$$

Where g refers to the energy group and i refers to the index of the corner or side. The homogeneous flux $\phi_{g,i}^{hom}$ in reflected or periodic assembly calculations is simply the average flux over the domain. Discontinuity factors obtained in such systems are often referred to as Assembly Discontinuity Factors (ADF). However, the nodal solution of the homogeneous flux is necessary, when the discontinuity factor is sought in a system where the node of interest is surrounded by other nodes (e.g. in a full-core model, or a heterogeneous fuel-reflector model such as shown in Figure 1. As discussed by [4], in order to obtain consistently generated DF, the nodal solver applied at this step has to be equivalent to the nodal solver the DF is produced for.

Solving the nodal equations in the triangles, and evaluating the DF according to (1) in such a reference system however requires knowledge of the heterogeneous side and corner net neutron currents and the nodal cross sections besides the heterogeneous flux. Furthermore, since modeling reference discontinuity factors involves placing fuel assemblies next to the region of interest, a correction is applied to triangles in contact with fuel elements [5]:

Figure 1. Example reflector system modeled with PHOENIX5. The magenta triangles highlight the region of interest. Reflected boundary conditions (BC) are applied everywhere besides the right periphery.

$$DF_{g,i} = \frac{ADF_{g,i}^{fuel}}{RDF_{g,i}^{fuel}} RDF_{g,i}^{refl} \quad (2)$$

To estimate the heterogeneous flux and net current for corners the following approximations were used:

$$J_c = J_{segment\ 1} + J_{segment\ 2} \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi_c = \frac{\Phi_{segment\ 1} + \Phi_{segment\ 2}}{2} \quad (4)$$

where the index c refers to the corner, and $segment\ 1$ and 2 refer to the side segments on the two side of the corner. For the side and segment fluxes and currents Serpent2 tallies were used readily as discussed in Section 3. Volume tallies were disregarded due to the expected low collision rate. However, the use of track-length tallies over corner-tip triangles will be explored in future work.

2.2. FULLCORE440 Benchmark

The core design, boron concentration, and control rod configuration can influence the importance of discontinuity factors. For example, a core with higher neutron leakage is expected to be more sensitive to reflector discontinuity factors. Nevertheless, our objective here is to provide insight rather than a generalized conclusion.

For this purpose, the VVER-440 FULLCORE benchmark was selected as the test case. Its relative simplicity allows for straightforward evaluation of neutronic behavior without the added complexity of thermal-hydraulic feedback or three-dimensional effects. The benchmark represents a two-dimensional core at nominal cold conditions. The reactor core comprises three fuel assembly types (1.6 wt%, 2.4 wt%, and 4.4 wt% fuel pins, with some pins containing 3.35 wt% Gd). The active core is surrounded by a radial reflector, described in detail in [6]. Two benchmark configurations are available: one with control rods and one without. In this work, due to space limitations, we present results only for the configuration with control rods. The reactor core layout is shown in Figure 2.

Additionally, a reduced model inspired by [7] was implemented to study the convergence of corner currents as a function of side segment length near the corner. This simplified system, shown in Figure 2, was chosen to enable faster data generation for this specific analysis.

Figure 2. Left: 60deg view of the FULLCORE440 benchmark, the outermost steel barrel is omitted from the image; Middle: reduced geometry with black boundary on the top, reflective elsewhere; Right: numbering scheme of the triangular lattice

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Serpent2 Implementation and Tallies

The VVER-440 FULLCORE benchmark was implemented in Serpent2 using ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data. The core model exploited its 30deg rotational symmetry to reduce computational effort. Serpent2 natively estimates discontinuity factors, along with heterogeneous side and corner fluxes and currents, only for hexagonal lattices. To overcome this limitation, we developed a Python method that automatically superimposes a triangular lattice on the full-core geometry and generates tallies for currents and fluxes along triangle sides and for segments around corners. POLCA8H is typically used with one row of reflectors, therefore the tallies were set to cover only the reflector region next to the active core. Nodal cross section data was also extracted for each triangle from Serpent2.

This process required careful bookkeeping; therefore, we established a fixed numbering scheme for triangles within each hexagon, as well as for sides and corners as shown in Figure 2. For simplicity in the initial implementation, each triangle was assigned its own set of tallies. Specifically, each triangle included three side flux and current tallies, along with six side-segment flux and current tallies at the corners, resulting in a total of 27 tallies per triangle, since incoming and outgoing currents were recorded separately.

Although some tallies are clearly redundant (for example, the out-going current on one side corresponds to the in-coming current for the neighbour triangle) this approach facilitated independent handling of each triangle for testing and sanity checks. In future work, the methodology will be updated to reduce the number of tallies by applying equivalence principles, which will also improve memory efficiency. All tallies were defined for two energy groups, with a thermal cutoff at 0.625 eV.

The detector outputs were parsed using `serpentTools` [8] and post-processed in Python. Raw tally results were used to compute heterogeneous net currents and fluxes for sides and corners, following the procedure described in Section 2. Finally, the heterogeneous currents, fluxes, and nodal data were passed to an in-house triangular diffusion solver, equivalent to the POLCA8H solver, to calculate homogeneous fluxes and determine the side and corner discontinuity factors. The obtained DCF were not corrected with the peripheral fuel assembly, since it was not intended to be used in subsequent nodal calculations of different core designs.

3.2. Sensitivity to Discontinuity Factors

To estimate the precision required for discontinuity factors, it is necessary to assess the sensitivity of core calculations to perturbations in these factors. For the sensitivity study, we used the PHOENIX5/POLCA8H code system with reflector models implemented in PHOENIX5.

The nodal solution depends on the ratios of discontinuity factors rather than their absolute values. Consequently, applying the same scaling factor to all discontinuity factors would leave the nodal solution unchanged. In contrast, our approach aims to emulate a scenario where the nodal data for fuel assemblies is considered accurate, while uncertainty exists only in the reflector data. Accordingly, the study aims to quantify how much error in reflector DCF estimation is acceptable, considering either a systematic bias in deterministic lattice codes or statistical uncertainties inherent to Monte Carlo methods, depending on the method used to obtain the DCF estimates.

The discontinuity factors provided to POLCA8H were directly perturbed, while all other nodal data remained unchanged. Perturbations were applied in two ways: (i) in a correlated manner, where all reflector discontinuity factors were modified by the same relative change, and (ii) in an uncorrelated manner, where each perturbation was sampled from a normal distribution centered around the discontinuity factor obtained from PHOENIX5. These two approaches represent the extremes; considering partially correlated perturbations would require prior knowledge of the degree of correlation, as discussed later.

We then analyzed the sensitivity of the system's multiplication factor and the root-mean-square error (RMSE) of the nodal core power distribution, relative to the unperturbed reference case.

3.3. Uncertainty Propagation

To evaluate the impact of the uncertainties in Monte Carlo-based tallies and nodal data on discontinuity factor uncertainties, we randomly sampled values using the mean and relative uncertainties provided by `Serpent2` and supplied these to the in-house nodal solver to compute the DCF. The sampling assumed normally distributed results. As noted in Section 3.1, even equivalent tallies were treated separately for individual triangles. However, in this investigation the DCF was not used for subsequent nodal calculations. Therefore, tally results and nodal data were applied to a single triangle to determine its side and corner DCF, and this outcome was independent of any neighboring triangle that shares sides or corners.

3.4. Tally Correlations and Convergence

Two issues were identified when using Monte Carlo methods for discontinuity factor calculations. The first concerns the appropriate segment length for estimating corner fluxes and currents (alternatively, an area-based tally could be considered). In regions with geometric symmetry around the corner point,

even a relatively long segment length is expected to provide a reasonable approximation using Eq. (3). By default, Serpent2 applies a segment length equal to 10 % of the side length near corners. For a VVER-440 hexagon with a pitch of 14.7 cm, this corresponds to approximately 0.85 cm. At Westinghouse Sweden, a similar segment length is typically used in BWR production calculations to estimate corner flux near detectors. However, a reflected fuel assembly naturally creates a symmetric system around the corner, whereas reflector hexagons often exhibit significant asymmetry, as illustrated in Figure 2. In PHOENIX5 reflector implementations, much shorter segments are employed to capture corner flux and current. Such small segments become impractical for Monte Carlo methods because prohibitively long simulations would be required to achieve sufficient scoring. Therefore, in this work we examine whether tallies based on the 10 % side length provide results close to the true values. For these investigations the reduced model was used (as shown in Figure 2.), to obtain reasonable uncertainties for short segments.

The second issue relates to the main topic of this paper: the propagation of errors from Monte Carlo-based discontinuity factors and nodal data uncertainties into nodal calculations. In this study, we assume that the uncertainties reported by Serpent2 are independent. However, scientific reasoning suggests that tallies associated with the same triangle are correlated, particularly for adjacent corner segments. Consequently, independent sampling of tally and nodal data within a single triangle is questionable. In principle, the flux and current fields should contain information on the degree of correlation between tallies. In practice, we attempted to assess this correlation using the tally flagging option in Serpent2. This investigation proved complex and inconclusive at the time of writing and is therefore omitted from this paper. We note, however, that the assumption of independent sampling may lead to an underestimation of discontinuity factor uncertainties.

Figure 3. Sensitivity of the k -effective (left) and the power (right) to the perturbation of discontinuity factors. “C” refers to corner discontinuity factors and “S” refers to side discontinuity factors

4. RESULTS

4.1. Sensitivity Results

The sensitivity of nodal calculations to perturbations in reflector discontinuity factors is shown in Figure 3. Applying a consistent perturbation to all factors (i.e., the same relative change) directly affects system leakage. A linear response is observed, as expected, although the reason why perturbations of corner and side factors influence system reactivity in opposite directions remains unclear. Since the root mean square error (RMSE) of the nodal power distribution is an absolute measure, this effect is not reflected there. However, the observation that the case where both corner and side factors are perturbed lies between the cases where only one type is perturbed suggests that the two effects partially compensate each other.

As noted earlier, the actual correlation among discontinuity factor values lies between the fully correlated and fully uncorrelated cases. Overall, the results indicate that uncertainty in discontinuity

factors is not highly penalizing. Even a 5 % perturbation leads to less than 50 pcm deviation in reactivity and about 0.5 % error in nodal power, which remains well within the acceptable limits for nodal codes.

4.2. Impact of Segment Length

The impact of segment length on net corner currents was investigated using the reduced model. This approach, intended to limit uncertainties, introduced some side effects. For corners located at reflection boundaries (i.e., corners #2-6, #3-4, #5-6, #6-4, where the first number refers to the triangle ID and the second to the corner ID as shown in Figure 2), the results were found to be artificial. In theory, the net current at a boundary should be zero for corners where the altitude of the triangle (the line from the corner to the midpoint of the opposite side) is perpendicular to the boundary. While the calculated net currents were generally close to zero, cases were observed where the sign of the net current changed as the segment length varied. At the time of writing, it remains under investigation whether this behavior is due to a methodological error or an indication that similar reduced models should be used with caution for corner current estimation.

Additionally, for corners near water–steel interfaces (such as corners #3-6, #4-4, #4-6, #5-6), the relationship between net current and segment length exhibited peaks or valleys. It is hypothesized that the fraction of the segment length within the steel significantly influences the estimated current. This effect is not specific to the reduced model and would persist even in full-core simulations.

The highlighted corners were excluded from Figure 4, which shows the normalized dependence of net corner current on segment length. These results provide useful consistency checks, as corners expected to agree due to system symmetry do so. In general, fast-group net currents are less sensitive to segment length; using 10 % of the side length results in only about a 4 % discrepancy. Drawing conclusions for thermal currents is more challenging because the uncertainty bounds are large, and within these bounds the values appear consistent.

Figure 4. Net current estimate dependence on side segment length. The values are normalized so that the net current at 4% triangle base length is unity.

4.3. Monte Carlo-based Discontinuity Factor Uncertainty

As a preliminary investigation, discontinuity factor (DCF) values were analyzed using a full-core simulation with 50,000 neutrons per cycle and 10,000 cycles. Although this is not an exceptionally large number of histories, it still requires approximately 500 times more computational time for a single state point compared to standard lattice-physics reflector calculations.

Uncertainties for side fluxes and nodal data were relatively small; however, as noted earlier, corner fluxes exhibited larger uncertainties, ranging from 1 % to 6 % in this simulation. The overall error in

DCF, propagated from tally and nodal data uncertainties, is shown in Figure 5 for three reflector hexagons. Fast-group DCF values were close to unity, as expected, since fast flux is typically spatially smooth. These values were estimated with negligible uncertainty. Thermal-group DCFs were less accurate, and in some locations where corners were very close to steel–water interfaces, corner discontinuity factors reached high values with uncertainties of up to 20–30%. This issue is likely related to the choice of side segment length rather than low number of histories.

Figure 5. Discontinuity factor and standard deviation in the reflector region (the central number is ID of the triangle) calculated with Serpent2

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

This paper examined the uncertainty associated with Monte Carlo-generated reflector discontinuity factors in triangular nodes. First, we analyzed the sensitivity of nodal simulations to reflector DCFs, and then we propagated Monte Carlo tally uncertainties into DCF estimates. It was observed that

moderate uncertainties of 2–3 % in DCF values remain acceptable. With sufficiently long Monte Carlo simulations, this level of accuracy is achievable for fast-group DCFs; however, thermal-group DCFs are more sensitive to corner tally uncertainty. In particular, when a triangle corner is located near an interface between materials of significantly different densities, estimating thermal DCFs becomes challenging, likely due to sensitivity to the segment length used for corner flux and current calculations.

Future work will focus on further exploring the sensitivity of DCFs to individual parameters, such as nodal data and current estimates. Additionally, we plan to investigate the impact of thermal-group DCF uncertainty on nodal calculations separately. This will help determine whether the observed uncertainties are acceptable or whether substantially longer computations per state point are required when using Monte Carlo-generated reflector DCFs instead of deterministic lattice-physics codes, which may introduce systematic bias in DCF estimates. Furthermore, we will explore the application of track-length tallies over corner-tip triangles to investigate whether the side segment based corner current estimation could be improved.

Finally, in this study we assumed that tally uncertainties are independent. However, scientific reasoning and preliminary investigations suggest that correlations exist, particularly among tallies within the same triangle. Therefore, future work will extend the methodology to include correlated uncertainty propagation.

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It is noted that Microsoft 365 Copilot was used in the preparation of this manuscript for editing and grammar checking. Furthermore, the same tool was used to speed up the post-processing of the results with Python.

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